

LASER-INDUCED GRAPHENE FIBRE SENSORS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Laser-induced graphene (LIG) technology has offered an innovative and convenient approach to produce porous graphene structures through a one-step laser scribing process from some polymer precursors. In this paper, continuous and freestanding graphene fibres were fabricated from micron-sized polyimide (PI) single filaments by laser irradiation. The morphology and microstructure of laser-induced graphene fibres (LIGFs) were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Raman spectroscopy and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The sensing properties of the freestanding LIGF sensor was evaluated by electromechanical coupling tensile test and shown excellent gauge sensitivity with a gauge factor of ~ 5.5 . With embedding the sensor into fiberglass prepreg laminates, only by the measurement of the electrical resistance, its use for multipurpose sensing in life-long (from manufacturing to failure) structural health monitoring (SHM) of high-performance polymeric composites was demonstrated. In the resin curing process, the resistance change of the embedded sensor provides valuable resin curing information. After integrated curing, the same sensor is able to map the strain/stress states and detect the failure of the host composite. In addition, the embedded sensor also is capable of monitor the damage accumulation in the fatigue loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene fibre, a macroscopic architecture assembled from two-dimensional (2D) microcosmic graphene sheets, has attracted considerable attention owing to its excellent properties originated from graphene such as unique and tunable nanostructure, high electrical and thermal conductivity, extraordinary elasticity and stiffness, ease of functionalization, and so on [1]. In addition, it also possesses the common characteristics of fibre, such as mechanical flexibility for textiles, lightweight, easy assembly, etc. [2]. Such fascinating merits therefore bring about a variety of novel strategies for self-sensing and health-state diagnosis functionalities for high-performance composites. Therefore, the development of scalable assembly methods of graphene fibre has become the core issue in the field of graphene fibres research, which is also the key to promote the integration of structure and function of graphene fibers.

Since the advent of graphene fibre in 2011[3], a variety of graphene fibre preparation methods have been developed mainly including: wet-spinning method [4], dry-spinning [5], one-step dimensionally confined hydrothermal strategy [6], dry film scrolling [7], and chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [8]. Despite tremendous advances, the above methods usually involve complicated raw materials synthetic, multiple steps in wet chemical or chemical vapor deposition processes, and post-processing such as GO reduction. These remaining issues limit their low cost, size, and production scalability for widespread industrial applications.

Recently, laser-induced graphene (LIG) method was reported as a facile and scalable approach to produce three-dimensional (3D) porous graphene structures through a one-step laser scribing process from some polymer precursors [9-11]. Compared with conventional methods for the fabrication of 3D graphene structures, LIG method is time-efficient, scalable, shape customizable, and free from high-temperature reaction conditions, solvent, or subsequent treatments. Take advantage of LIG benefits, a wide range of multifunctional sensors have been reported for SHM applications. With polyimide paper (PI paper) as the precursor medium, Wang et al. prepared a macroscopic 2D graphene paper structure

and integrated to fibre-reinforced polymeric composites with wing-like and curved appearance. Meanwhile, the embedded graphene paper was further proved can be used for through-life monitoring of glass fibre composite laminates [10]. Sha et al. direct in situ 3D printed freestanding 3D graphene foams based on laser sintering of metal powder [12]. In comparison with the aforementioned LIG 2D or 3D sensors, one-dimensional (1D) sensors have outstanding embeddable and non-invasive characteristics for polymeric composites. However, the preparation of macroscopic 1D graphene fibre by LIG method hasn't been reported in the literature.

Aiming to further advance this emerging field, we report a simple and scalable approach to produce macroscopic 1D graphene fibre by processing PI single filament via LIG. In comparison with the previously development fabrication methods of 1D assembleable flexible sensors, such as spraying coating [13-14], spinning [4-5], and dip coating [15-16], the fabrication of LIGF is simple, cost-effective and environment benign. Moreover, when embedded into polymeric composites, the LIGF can be used as a multipurpose sensor for life-long (from manufacturing to failure) SHM of the host structure. A series of combined mechanical/electrical tests were performed to evaluate the sensing capability of freestanding and embedded LIGF sensors. It is believed that the 1D LIGF sensor, which is readily for large-scale preparation and assembly, is a vantage technique for future applications in local damage detection and strain/stress mapping of composite materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Fabrication and characterization of LIGF

Figure 1. Fabrication of LIGF. (a) A bundles of scattered PI fibres. (b) Schematic diagram of LIGF process. (c) Optical photographs of LIGFs with different shapes (Top, Scale = 50 μm ; Low, Scale = 200 μm). (d) Schematic illustration of LIGF fabrication including the concept of roll-to-roll manufacturing.

As schematically depicted in Figure 1, LIGF was fabricated through laser irradiation by directly converting a PI single filament into a freestanding LIGF under ambient conditions, in which the PI single filament was hand-peeled off from a bundles of PI fibers (Cat.# Yil-H, PolyKing Co., single filament 1.6dtex and 16 μm in diameter) as shown on Figure 1a. Two ends of the PI single filament were glued on a glass slide by double-sided adhesive tape, and then under the computer aided control, the PI single filament was scribed by a 10.6 μm CO₂ laser (DLS 2.3, Universal Laser Systems, Inc.) in a line-by-line mode (50 μm in line space) as depicted in Figure 1b. The laser system was operated in a vector mode with the fixed power set at 0.4W, scan rate set at 2inch/s, and pixel per inch (PPI) set at 520. Figure 1c shows the optical photograph of the obtained freestanding LIGF (top) and LIGF with arbitrary bending shape (bottom left), circled shape (bottom middle) and braided (bottom right), indicating the excellent flexibility of LIGF. The diameter of these freestanding fibers is only about 18

μm . Considering the tremendous advantages in terms of convenient, efficient and low cost, we highly expect the escalation of lab-scale process to roll-to-roll continuous manufacturing for future large-scale production of LIGF, which is schematically shown in Figure 1d.

To characterize the laser-induced structure, LIGFs were examined by SEM, TEM and Raman spectra. The morphologies of LIGFs were observed and imaged by using optical microscope (Nikon SMZ800N) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM 7001F) with an acceleration voltage set at 10 kV. Before SEM imaging, the sample mounted on a metal stub was sputter-coated with gold. LIGFs were immersed in alcohol and then subjected to mild sonication by a bath sonicator (KQ100DE, KunShan Ultrasonic Instruments Co., Ltd.) to obtain a dilute suspension for investigating their size information at nano scale. This obtained suspension was dropped onto Cu grids and dried at room temperature to prepare the samples for TEM imaging. TEM images were taken using an 80 KeV JEM 2100F (JEOL Inc.). The 3D graphene structures of LIGF also were characterized by Raman scattering spectroscopy, the spectra of which were collected by a Horiba HR800 Raman microscope with a 532 nm excitation laser at the power of 5 Mw.

2.2 Fabrication of glass fiber reinforced composite laminates assembled with LIGF sensor

To integrate a LIGF sensor into polymeric composites as part of preform, a LIGF sensor was placed between two layers of fiberglass prepreg (GF-PL-290-100, Easy Composites Ltd.) and integrated curing as shown in Figure 2. Specifically, 2-layer rectangular shaped prepreps, which is a $5\text{ cm} \times 2\text{ cm}$ size, were first stacked into a multilayer structure with the LIGF sensor and gold wire electrodes ($\sim 50\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter, LOT # 29001, California Fine Wire Company) being embedded. Subsequent to the prepreg stacking and sensor embedding, the prepreg stack was then inserted into a vacuum bag to induce the resin curing process. The vacuum bagging process was operated under one standard atmospheric pressure (0.1 MPa) and at a vacuum oven. According to the vendor suggestion, the curing temperature was first ramped from room temperature to $120\ ^\circ\text{C}$ and then maintained at $120\ ^\circ\text{C}$ isothermally for 2 h. During the curing process, the resistance of the embedded LIGF sensor was simultaneously recorded by a Keithley 7510 Sourcemeter® controlled by a homemade LabVIEW user interface.

Figure 2. Fabrication procedures of glass fiber reinforced composite laminates embedded with LIGF sensor.

2.3 Piezoresistivity Evaluation of LIGF sensor for SHM of GFRC laminates

The piezoresistivity of a freestanding LIGF sensor was tested at room temperature by a coupled electrical-cyclic tensile testing method. In the testing, the LIGF sensor was glued on the middle of a $20\text{mm} \times 5\text{mm}$ rectangular PI film (Kapton, $25\ \mu\text{m}$ in thickness) with silver paste applied on the two ends as electrodes and then the sample subjected to a 10-cyclic tension deformation applied by a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA Q850, TA Instrument Inc.). For DMA measurement, the gauge length was set at 5mm, the amplitude of the displacement set was 0.01mm, and the displacement rate

set at 0.1mm/min. At the same time, the sensor resistance was measured in-situ using a Keithley 7510 Sourcemeter® controlled by a homemade LabVIEW user interface.

The sensing capability of the embedded LIGF sensor was evaluated with an E44.104 tensile machine (500N load cell, MTS Systems Corp.) to apply varied modes of deformation to the composite laminate samples at room temperature, including cyclic tensile tests with the maximum strain varied from 1% to 3.5%, cyclic tensile tests with the maximum strain fixed at 2.5% for 10 cycles, tension-to-failure tests, and fatigue failure-cycle tests with the maximum strain fixed at 2%. For each test, the typical gauge length was set at 20mm. For the cyclic tensile tests with the varied maximum strain, with the increase of maximum strain, the corresponding displacement rates were stepwise increase from 2mm/min to 7mm/min. For the cyclic tensile tests with the fixed maximum strain and tension to failure test, the displacement rates were set at 5mm/min. For the fatigue failure-cycle tests, the displacement rates were set at 12mm/min. A Keithley 7510 Sourcemeter® controlled by a home-established LabVIEW user interface was used simultaneously for acquiring the sensor resistance during mechanical loading.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Structural Characterization and piezoresistivity evaluation of the standalone LIGF

Figure 3(a) shows the surface SEM images of LIGF under low and high magnifications, revealing the macrography appearance and foam-like structure with non-uniformly distributed porous micromorphology resulting from the rapid liberation of gaseous products, which is similar to LIG from other PI precursors, such as Kapton [9] or PI paper [10]. To further investigate the micro and nano structure of LIGF, TEM images were taken. Figure 3 (b) shows the TEM images of LIGF under low- and high-resolution. It is visible that thin LIG flakes with few-layer features. Moreover, ripple-like wrinkled structures can be observed from the surface of the flakes. The structures of LIGF were further revealed by Raman, as shown in Figure 3 (c), the Raman spectrum shows three distinguished D (roughly at 1340cm^{-1}), G (roughly at 1569cm^{-1}) and 2D (roughly at 2680cm^{-1}) peaks, suggests a large degree of graphene formation during the engraving process on the PI single filament. However, no clear peaks were seen for the pristine PI monofilament within the range of $500\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure 3. Structural characterization of freestanding LIGF (a) SEM images of LIGF at low (scale = $100\ \mu\text{m}$) and high magnification (inset, scale = $1\ \mu\text{m}$). (b) TEM images of LIGF under low (scale = $100\ \text{nm}$) and high magnification (inset, scale = $5\ \text{nm}$). (c) Comparison of Raman spectra between LIGF and pristine PI single filament.

As detailed in the Experimental Methods, upon application of a cyclic tensile strain ramped from 0 to 0.01mm at the electrode ends of LIGF sensor by a dynamic mechanical analyzer (Figure 4a), the electromechanical coupling experiment was carried out to evaluate the strain sensing properties of the freestanding LIGF sensor. As depicted in Figure 4b, the sensor resistance changed instantaneously with the force application and is linearly proportional to the applied tensile strain. According to the definition of the gauge factor (GF) of a piezoresistive sensor as presented in Ref. 13-14, the GF of the freestanding LIGF sensor was evaluated to be 5.495 ± 0.034 . This value is superior to that of a standalone glass SWCNT-FibSen sensor as reported in our previous work [13].

Figure 4. (a) Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) setup for testing the piezoresistivity of the freestanding LIGF sensor. (b) The coupled electrical-cyclic tensile test results of the freestanding LIGF sensor.

3.2 Embedded LIGF sensor for Monitoring the Curing process of Polymeric Composites

LIGF has continuous, small diameter and scalable piezoresistive properties, which enable it noninvasive embedded in high-performance composites. Therefore, we broaden the application of LIGF in through-life monitoring of fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites from manufacturing to utilization and failure. First, in the curing process, the real-time resistance change of the embedded LIGF sensor was recorded as shown in Figure 5. One can see that there are evident two stages of the resistance change. In the first stage the sensor resistance rapidly increases when the temperature ramped from room temperature to stated curing temperature. In the following second stage, during which the sample was maintained thermostatic, the sensor resistance initially goes through a rapid decrease and then gradually reaches a stable value. As our previous studies have revealed [13-14, 17], the initial resistance increase is due to the penetration/infiltration of resin molecules into the 3D porous structure of LIGF as the temperature increase, resulting the expansion and even breakage of the conductive pathway in LIGF. What's more, the decrease of subsequent resistance is attributed to cross-linking reaction of resin, causing the shrinkage of the resin matrix and reconstitution of the conductive network in LIGF. Therefore, the results shown in Figure 5 demonstrate the unique applications of LIGF-sensor in in-situ monitoring the resin curing process, and therefore to provide a simple method for real-time quality assurance of composite manufacturing.

Figure 5. Resin curing process of the epoxy/glass fiber composite registered by the real-time resistance change of embedded LIGF sensor.

3.3 Embedded LIGF sensor for SHM of the polymeric composite structure

After molding, the embedded LIGF sensor can also be used as the piezoresistive or strain sensor for monitoring the mechanical loading/deformation of the host structure. Figure 6a shows the real-time resistance variation of the embedded LIGF sensor as the host composite laminates was deformed to stepwise increased strain from 1% to 3.5%. Obviously, the variation of resistance displayed an increase tendency with increasing tensile strain and showed good linear relationship with the applied tensile strain, indicating that when the strain is no more than 3.5%, both the laminate and the sensor are subjected to elastic deformation.

To further evaluate sensor performance, a coupled electrical-cyclic tensile test was performed with tensile strain ramped from 0 to 2.5%. As shown in Figure 6b, electrical responses in every cycle is synchronized with mechanical loadings and unloading, indicating the linear and reproducible piezoresistive performance of the embedded LIGF sensor. To quantify the sensor sensitivity, GF of the embedded LIGF sensor was evaluated according to the aforementioned method. Averaged from the 10 cycles, the embedded LIGF sensor had a GF of approximate 0.17 under 2.5% tensile strain. It is worth noting that the sensitivity of the assembled LIGF sensor has a significantly reduced compared with that of the standalone LIGF sensor. The famous Poisson effect is considered to be the cause of this phenomenon, at least partly. When the laminate is subjected to tension parallel to the direction of the embedded LIGF sensor, the LIGF will elongate along the direction of load and shorten in the direction perpendicular to load. Elongation deformation lead to slippage of conductive layer and a longer distance between the neighboring disconnected graphene layer, which causes the sensor resistance increase, and the shorten induces a decrease of the sensor resistance by decreasing the distance between graphene layers. These two opposite effects act simultaneously to result in a smaller sensor resistance change and therefore a reduced GF as compared to the standalone LIGF. In addition, the different nature of the graphene layers contacts in the standalone and the embedded sensors may also play a role regarding their significantly different gauge sensitivity. In the standalone sensor, there is a direct graphene layers contact, but in the embedded sensor, there is very likely an insulating layer of resin molecules to modulate the graphene layers contacts. Therefore, the freestanding LIGF and the embedded LIGF sensors may have different sensing mechanisms and piezoresistive responses.

Figure 6. Piezoresistive response of LIGF sensor embedded in epoxy/glass fiber laminate under (a) cyclic tensile test with the maximum strain increased stepwise from 1% to 2.5%. (b) 10-cycle-tensile test with the maximum strain at 2.5%.

In the above research, we found that the assembled LIGF sensor have excellent linearity and reproducibility of resistance-strain relationship at small deformation. After that, the sensing capability of the embedded LIGF sensor during the laminate tension to failure were investigated. Figure 7 depicts the variation of embedded LIGF sensor resistance and laminates tensile strength during tension to

failure testing. It is observed that the resistance of the assembled LIGF sensor varies monotonously with the deformation of the composite laminates. Specifically, when the strain is less than 4.1%, the host laminate shows an elastic deformation behavior which is captured faithfully by a linear increase of the LIGF sensor resistance (GF=0.29). With further increasing the strain level above 4.1%, strain-softening is observed from the strain-tensile strength curve of composite laminate. That is to say, the tensile modulus of the laminate at strain greater than 4.1% is less than that at strain less than 4.1%. In consistent with the strain-softening transition, the piezo-resistivity sensitivity of the LIGF sensor is also increased (GF=19.18). When the strain further increased to 5.83%, the failure of the laminate occurs. At the same time, one can observe that a dramatical increase of the sensor resistance (GF=Infinity). The result shown in Figure 7 suggests the value of the embedded LIGF sensor in detecting the different failure modes, such as fiber/matrix delamination and crack initiation, of the polymeric composites.

Figure 7. Tension to failure test of the fully cured epoxy/fiber glass laminate embedded with a LIGF sensor.

In addition to being able to monitor the state of the laminates under different deformation, LIGF sensor can also be used to monitor the fatigue damage accumulation of the laminates. Figure 8 shows real-time variation of embedded sensor resistance and laminates modulus during fatigue loading. It can be observed that a decrease of the stiffness of the laminates is accompanied by an increasing resistance of the embedded LIGF sensor. It should be noted that the stiffness of the laminate is expressed over the dynamic residual modulus, which is measured in terms of the imposed maximum load in every loading cycle. Basically, the dynamic modulus of laminates exhibit three-stage characteristics during fatigue failure, which is consistent with previous studies on glass fiber reinforced composites [18]. Correspondingly, one also can observe three-stage characteristics of the embedded LIGF resistance during fatigue life. Hence, it can be concluded that the change in resistance correlates with the crack density during fatigue life. What's more, one remarkable concerning fact that the fatigue failure of the laminate could be detected by an abrupt increase of the LIGF resistance.

Figure 8. Real-time normalized residual modulus changes of the laminate and resistance changes of embedded LIGF sensor during fatigue loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we demonstrated a new fabrication of freestanding LIGF sensors by an innovative and simple LIG technology, using PI single filaments as precursors. This technique offers a cost-effective, facile and scalable process, which can realize the roll-to-roll consecutive manufacturing of LIGFs. The freestanding LIGF sensors are micron size, lightweight and continuous, these properties enable them to be readily and noninvasively assembled into polymeric composite structures. Furthermore, the coupled electrical–mechanical test proved that the freestanding LIGF sensor have excellent gauge sensitivity.

Taking advantage of these merits, the LIGF sensors were integrated into laminates to demonstrate their utility for life-long SHM of polymeric composite structure. Only by the measurement of the electrical resistance and without additional sensors, the embedded LIGF sensor is able to provide the in-situ resin curing information in the process of composite resin curing. After the integrated curing process, the incremental and cyclic tensile tests show that the embedded LIGF sensor is useful for mapping the strain state, and the tensile to failure tests as well as fatigue test shows that the embedded LIGF sensor can also detect the micro-crack initiation and accumulation in the host composites.

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